

TABLE 2—ASSIGNMENTS AND SHIFTS OF IR BANDS (CM⁻¹) OF THE LIGAND AND COMPLEXES

Ligand	Complex	Assignments	Shifts in the frequency and change in intensity
3 320m	—	In ligand due to $\nu(\text{N-H})$ asym and $\nu(\text{N-H})$ sym	Disappears or broadening
3 100m	—		Disappears or broadening
1 670s I	1670 $\pm$ 10	Contribution of $\delta(\text{NH})$	Broadening of $\delta(\text{N-H})$ band
1 580m I	—	Chelation through N=C-S moiety thioamide band I	Disappears or becomes broad
1 540m I	—		
1 360m II	1360 $\pm$ 10	Coordination through N=C-S and contribution of thioamide band II	Shifting by 10 cm ⁻¹
1 250m	1250-20	Showing the election drift from N-N(azide) band	Shifts to lower wave number
1 150m III	1150 $\pm$ 10	Coordination through NCS group, band III	
830w	—	Contribution of $\delta(\text{N-N-C-})$	Disappears
750w IV	—	Coordination through (C-S) group, band IV	Disappears
540m	—	Contribution of $\tau(\text{N-N})$	Disappears
450m	—	Contribution of $\tau(\text{N-N})$	Disappears
	500	$\nu(\text{M-N})$	
	340+30	$\nu(\text{M-S})$	

possibility of spin-free configuration ($b_{1g}^2 e_g^2 a_{1g}^1 b_{1g}^1$). Orbital configuration to the magnetic moment in square-planar complexes, is expected to be small as orbital angular momentum among the d-orbital is largely quenched by low symmetry D_{4h} . Thus the absence of transition band and the value of magnetic moment (4.90 B.M.) suggest square-planar arrangement of the ligand around Mn^{2+} ion.

The observed value of magnetic moment 2.84 B.M., suggests the presence of two unpaired electron in Ni^{2+} complex. There are bands at 31 250, 37 593, 20 576 and 19 230 cm⁻¹ in the electronic spectrum of Ni^{2+} complex. Bands at 31 250 and 37 593 cm⁻¹ may be due to charge-transfer band. The band at (486 nm) 20 576 cm⁻¹ suggest the existence of ground state ${}^3A_{2g}$ for octahedral Ni^{2+} complex¹⁰. Because the ratio of the frequencies 20 576 to 19 230 cm⁻¹ is found to be more sensitive to give the free ion value of $B' 616$ cm⁻¹ compared to the reported value of $B 1 080$ cm⁻¹ for Ni^{2+} complex⁹. The band at 20 576 (ν_2) and 19 230 cm⁻¹ (ν_1) can be assigned due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\text{P})$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\text{F})$ transitions for Ni^{2+} octahedral complex. The value of $10 Dq$ is found to be 20 328 cm⁻¹ which is extremely high compared to the reported value 12 000 cm⁻¹ for ethylenediamine for octahedral Ni^{2+} complex⁹.

The value of magnetic moment observed in the Co^{2+} complex 4.80 B.M., suggest the octahedral geometry of the complex⁹. There are two bands in the electronic transition at 20 408 and 18 867 cm⁻¹. The bands at 20 408 and 18 867 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(\text{P})$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ transitions. The ratio of frequencies 20 408 to 18 867 cm⁻¹ is found to be more sensitive to give the free ion value of $B' 739$ cm⁻¹, compared to the reported value of $B 1 120$ cm⁻¹ for Co^{2+} complex.

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Thermodynamic Stability of some Rare Earths Complexes with Tyrosine. A Polarographic Study

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VARIOUS complexing reagents have been employed in the polarographic determination of rare earths¹⁻⁶. In continuation, the author now reports the thermodynamic stability of Ce^{3+} ,

Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} complexes with tyrosine on a dropping mercury electrode.

Experimental

All chemicals used were AnalaR grade. The ligand solution was prepared in double-distilled water. The metals solutions were prepared by dissolving their oxides in minimum amount of hydrochloric acid and were standardised with EDTA⁷. The overall concentrations of potassium chloride, gelatin and rare earth metal ion in the test electrolytic solution were kept constant at 1.0M, 0.01% and 2.0 mM, respectively. The concentration of ligand was varied from 1.0 to 100 mM in each case. Ionic strength (μ) was fixed at 1.0, adjusted with potassium chloride. Hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide were used to adjust pH of the test solution at 2.70 ± 0.02 .

Polarograms were recorded on an automatic pen recording polarograph (C.I.C., India), the capillary used had a 'm' value of 2.15 mg s^{-1} and drop time of 3.10 s at 44.0 cm effective height of the mercury ($m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.15 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$). Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the solution for removing the dissolved oxygen. A Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used to measure pH of the solution. All the measurements were made at 25 and 35°, thermostatically controlled.

Results and Discussion

Ce^{III} , Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} give a well defined three-electron reversible reduction waves at pH 2.70 ± 0.02 in 1.0 M potassium chloride with 0.01% gelatin being used as a maximum suppressor. The difference of $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ was 20 ± 1 mV for Ce^{III} , Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} and their complexes indicating the reversibility¹¹ of the electrode process. The nature of the waves for metal ions and their complexes was found to be diffusion-controlled as revealed from the straight line plots of i_d vs $\sqrt{h}$.

The half-wave potential shifted to more negative value on increasing the concentration of ligand. The method of Lingane¹² was used to determine the formation of 1:1 complexes of Ce^{III} , Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} with tyrosine. Thermodynamic parameter (ΔG) was calculated from the thermodynamic relations¹³ and given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS (LOG K) AND FREE ENERGY CHANGE (ΔG) OF Ce^{III} , Pr^{III} AND Nd^{III} COMPLEXES WITH TYROSINE

$\mu = 1.0 \text{ KCl}$	log K		ΔG kcal mole ⁻¹	
	25°	35°	25°	35°
Ce^{III}	3.52	3.00	-4.83	-4.25
Pr^{III}	4.35	4.12	-5.96	-5.84
Nd^{III}	4.60	4.35	-6.30	-6.16

The order of stability of complexes was found to be $\text{Ce}^{III} < \text{Pr}^{III} < \text{Nd}^{III}$, which is due to lanthanide contraction⁶.

The gain in the free energies suggest that the complexes are not facilitated at higher temperature⁶.

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Thermal Decomposition of $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$

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A number of hydrates of cerium chloride including the heptahydrate cerium chloride ($\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) are known to exist¹. On heating, cerium chloride is reported to lose water followed by HCl. The present investigation deals with the study of the thermal decomposition of $\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, both isothermal and non-isothermal to understand the nature of coordination of water molecules and the identity of the ultimate decomposition product. The final decomposition product has been analysed by X-ray diffractometry.

Experimental

$\text{CeCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (G.R., E. Merck, 98.5%) was used without further purification. For the isothermal study, a known amount of the compound (500 mg)